

**The Role of Parent Brand Perceptions in Consumers' Evaluations of Brand Extension:
A Study on Perceived Fit and Brand Attitude**

Correspond author: Asst. Prof. Dr. Ali KÖROĞLU

Tokat Gaziosmanpaşa University, Tokat / Türkiye

ORCID: 0000-0003-4021-6300

Independent Researcher Mehmet TEMİR

Tokat / Türkiye

ORCID: 0000-0001-7259-335X

Abstract

Today, intense competition and the high costs of establishing a new brand can lead businesses to implement brand extension strategies. However, brand extension strategies don't always end in success. Consumer adoption of a brand in a new product category can depend on several factors. The aim of this study is to examine the brand-based cognitive and psychological mechanisms that influence consumers' attitudes towards brand extension and their purchase intentions. For this purpose, research was conducted on 472 people living in Tokat province. Research data was collected through a survey form. The obtained data were analyzed using structural equation modeling (SEM). The findings indicate that parent brand awareness, parent brand image, and parent brand trust positively effect perceived fit. Perceived fit also has a positive effect on attitudes toward the brand extension and brand extension purchase intention. Attitude toward brand extension positively effects brand extension purchase intention. Attitude toward the extension brand mediates the relationship between perceived fit and brand extension purchase intention. It is believed that the results obtained will make significant contributions to the literature in the field of brand management and for businesses implementing brand extension strategies.

Keywords: Brand awareness, brand image, brand trust, perceived fit, brand extension.

1. Introduction

Today, developing a new product involves significant risks such as intense competition, high costs, and failure. Many products fail to deliver the expected performance and are withdrawn from the market shortly after their introduction (Aaker & Keller, 1990). Therefore, businesses want to leverage their existing brand value when launching a new product to the market. One strategy businesses use to leverage their existing brand value is brand extension. Brand extension is used by businesses because using a strong brand name in a new product category leads to faster consumer adoption and a competitive advantage.

Furthermore, brand extension strategies are not always successful. While some brand extension strategies are successful, others are unsuccessful and may even harm the parent brand. For a strong brand, entering a new product category may not be enough on its own. Consumers can expect a logical, consistent, and harmonious relationship between the parent brand and the extension brand. This has led to perceived fit occupying a central position in the brand extension literature (Aaker & Keller, 1990).

While the importance of perceived fit to brand extension strategy has long been recognized, there is no consensus on the specific factors that contribute to its emergence. While many studies focus on the similarity between product categories, the role of cognitive and affective consumer perceptions of the parent brand in forming perceptions of conformity has been less explored.

Although the importance of perceived fit for brand extension strategy has long been known, there is no consensus on the factors that cause this perception. While much research focuses on the similarity of product categories, the role of cognitive and affective consumer perceptions of the parent brand in the formation of perceived fit has been less studied. In particular, different results have been obtained regarding the role of factors directly related to brand equity, such as brand image, brand awareness, and brand trust, in the formation of perceived fit (Keller, 1993; Chaudhuri & Holbrook, 2001).

The success of a brand extension strategy cannot be explained solely by perceived fit. Consumer attitudes toward the brand extension can also influence its success. While the impact of perceived fit on the success of brand extension strategy has been established, the specific psychological mechanisms behind this effect are still under investigation. In particular, there are a limited number of studies examining the role of attitude toward the brand extension in the influence of perceived fit on purchase intention.

The aim of this research is to fill this gap. The study examines the effect of parent brand awareness, parent brand image, and parent brand trust on perceived fit; and tests the effect of perceived fit on attitudes towards the brand extension and the extension brand purchase intention. In addition, the mediating role of attitudes towards the brand extension between perceived fit and the extension brand purchase intention is evaluated. In this respect, the study makes two important contributions to the brand extension literature. The first contribution is that perceived fit is explained not only in terms of product similarity but also in the context of consumer perceptions towards the parent brand. The second contribution is that it provides a better understanding of the consumer decision-making mechanism in the brand extension process by examining the mediating role of attitudes towards the brand extension in the formation of the extension brand purchase intention. The research findings are expected to contribute both to businesses developing brand extension strategies and to academic studies in the field of brand management.

2. Literature review

In highly competitive environments, businesses seeking to avoid the costs and risks of developing new products leverage their existing brand names by using them in new product categories, thereby attempting to protect themselves from these risks and expenses. This approach, known as brand extension strategy, is a significant marketing strategy that increases the likelihood of new products being accepted by consumers. Brand extension strategy can

enable new products to be adopted more quickly in the market by transferring the experience, knowledge, and associations of the existing brand to the new products (Aaker & Keller, 1990). However, brand extension strategies are not always successful, and their success depends on how consumers perceive the relationship between the main brand and the extension brand.

Consumers' knowledge and perceptions of the parent brand play a significant role in evaluating the fit between the parent brand and the extension brand. One of these consumer perceptions, brand awareness, is the level at which consumers recognize and remember a brand (Keller, 1993). Brands with high brand awareness can positively influence consumers' perceptions by creating strong and accessible associations in their minds. Consumer familiarity with the brand can ensure that the extension product is perceived as fit with the parent brand identity (Laroche et al., 1996; Zeng et al., 2019). Based on this information in the literature, the following hypothesis has been developed:

H1. Parent brand awareness has a positive effect on perceived fit.

Brand image is one of the key factors influencing perceived fit. Brand image is the sum of all associations, perceptions, and thoughts that consumers have about a brand (Keller, 1993). Brand extensions undertaken by businesses with a strong brand image are often viewed more positively by consumers. This is because the positive associations of the parent brand are transferred to the extension product, making it easier for consumers to accept it (Salinas & Perez, 2009). Specifically, it can strengthen perceived fit by enabling consumers to forge a more meaningful association between the parent brand and the extension product. Based on this information in the literature, the following hypothesis has been developed:

H2. Parent brand image has a positive effect on perceived fit.

Another factor that can influence the success of brand extension by affecting perceived fit is brand trust. Brand trust is consumers' belief that a brand will fulfill its promises and deliver the expected performance (Chaudhuri & Holbrook, 2001). Consumers perceive new product launches from brands they trust as lower risk, which increases their likelihood of accepting the extension product. Research also shows that high brand trust leads to a more positive perception of the fit between the parent brand and the extension brand (Keller & Aaker, 1992; Reast, 2003; Zeng et al., 2019). Based on this information in the literature, the following hypothesis has been developed:

H3. Parent brand trust has a positive effect on perceived fit.

Perceived fit is one of the most important elements in the success of a brand extension strategy due to its impact on consumer evaluations. Perceived fit is the perceived level of consistency, similarity, and appropriateness between the parent brand and the extension product (Smith & Park, 1992). Research indicates that consumers have higher attitudes toward and purchase intentions towards the extension brand when they perceive a high degree of fit between the parent brand and the extension product (Aaker & Keller, 1990; Buil et al., 2009). Numerous studies in the literature highlight that perceived fit positively influences attitudes toward brand extension and purchase intention (Ashton & Scott, 2011; Czellar, 2003; Salinas & Perez, 2009; Sarasvuo et al., 2023; Zeng et al., 2019). Based on this information in the literature, the following hypotheses have been developed:

H4. Perceived fit has a positive effect on extension brand purchase intention.

H5. Perceived fit has a positive effect on attitude toward brand extension.

In the brand extension process, the key element shaping consumer behavior is attitude towards the extension product. Attitude, one of the strongest determinants of consumer behavior, refers to individuals' positive or negative evaluations of a brand, object, or product. Consumers' positive evaluations and emotional responses to the extension product are influential in shaping their purchase intentions. Numerous studies in the literature have shown that a positive attitude towards the extension product is a determining factor in purchase intention (Goh, 2010; Riley et al., 2015; Yudianto, 2022). Based on this information in the literature, the following hypothesis has been developed:

H6. Attitude toward the brand extension has a positive effect on the brand extension purchase intention.

Consumers who perceive a high level of fit between the parent brand and the extension product evaluate the extension product as more meaningful, more reliable, and more consistent with the brand identity. This situation reinforces positive attitudes toward the extension product (Buil et al., 2009). While the literature states that perceived fit is a significant factor in branding adoption, it emphasizes that this effect will manifest through positive attitudes developed towards the branding. Because consumers first evaluate the parent brand against the extension brand, develop an attitude towards the extension brand as a result of this evaluation, and finally translate this attitude into purchase intention (Czellar, 2003). Consumers who perceive a high level of fit between the parent brand and the extension brand develop more positive attitudes toward the extension brand, and these attitudes can translate into purchase intention (Aaker & Keller, 1990; Czellar, 2003; Buil et al., 2009). Therefore, the effect of perceived fit on extension brand purchase intention is expected to occur not only directly but also indirectly through attitudes towards the extension brand. Based on this information in the literature, the following hypothesis has been developed:

H7. Attitudes toward the extension brand mediate the relationship between perceived fit and the brand extension purchase intention.

The literature on brand awareness, brand image, brand trust, perceived fit, brand attitude and brand trust, and their total and indirect effects on purchase intention, has led us to conclude that brand attitude may play a mediating role in the relationships between these variables. Based on this the research model is developed in Figure 1 to test this effect empirically.

Figure 1. Research model

3. Methodology

3.1. Survey questionnaire design

A survey form was used as a data collection tool in the research. The first part of the survey form includes statements aimed at determining participants' gender, age, education level, and monthly household income. The second part of the survey includes statements aimed at determining parent brand trust, parent brand awareness, parent brand image, perceived alignment, attitude towards the extension brand, and purchase intention for the extension brand, all related to a well-known brand implementing a brand extension strategy and the extension brand itself.

To measure parent brand trust, a four-items scale developed by Delgado-Ballester (2004) was used. A five-items scale taken from the study by Saydan et al. (2011) was used to measure parent brand awareness. To measure parent brand image, a six-items scale developed by Escalas and Bettman (2005) was used. To measure perceived fit, the four-items scale developed by Bhat and Reddy (2001) was used. To measure attitudes toward the extension brand, the cognitive dimension of the eight-items brand attitude scale developed by Wu and Wang (2011) was used. To measure extension brand purchase intention, a four-items scale developed by Yoo and Donthu (2001) was used. All scales are prepared in a 5-point Likert style.

3.2. Data collection and sampling

This study, conducted to examine the relationships between parent brand trust, parent brand image, parent brand awareness, perceived fit, attitude towards extension brand, and extension brand purchase intention, used a survey form as a data collection tool. The survey form was

administered face-to-face to participants living in Tokat province between July 30, 2024 and August 20, 2024. The sample was selected using convenience sampling. By the end of the allotted time, 472 people had completed the survey. Therefore, the sample for this study consists of 472 people. The population of Tokat province is approximately 600,000. According to the sample size calculation method, 384 people are considered sufficient for a sample size in a population of 600,000 (Yazıcıoğlu & Erdoğan, 2004). Therefore, the sample size for this study is sufficient.

3.3. Reliability of the questionnaire

Cronbach's Alpha values were considered to determine the reliability of the scales. A Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.70 or higher indicates a high level of reliability for the scales (Gürbüz & Şahin, 2017). The analysis revealed that the Cronbach's Alpha values for the parent brand trust scale were 0.905; for the parent brand image scale, 0.964; for the parent brand awareness scale, 0.916; for the perceived fit scale, 0.955; for the attitude towards extension brand scale, 0.928; and for the extension brand purchase intention scale, 0.951. Therefore, the reliability levels of all scales are quite high.

4. Results analysis

4.1. Respondents' profile

The demographic characteristics of the participants in the study are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic information of respondents

Items	Categories	Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender	Male	234	49,6
	Female	238	50,4
Age	18-27	108	22,9
	28-37	120	25,4
	38-47	110	23,3
	48-57	81	17,2
	≥58	53	11,2
Education	Primary/Middle School	48	10,2
	High School	118	25,0
	Associate Degree	121	25,6
	Bachelor's Degree	146	30,9
	Postgraduate Degree	39	8,3
Household Income	≤22.105 TL	74	15,7
	22.106 TL-44.000 TL	87	18,4
	44.001 TL-66.000 TL	150	31,8
	66.001 TL-88.000 TL	94	19,9
	≥88.001 TL	67	14,2
Total		472	100

4.2. Convergent validity

To test the structure of the research model, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), composite reliability (CR), and average variance extracted (AVE) values were examined. An AVE value

greater than 0.50 indicates that convergent validity is achieved, and a CR value greater than 0.70 indicates that internal consistency is achieved (Hair et al., 2014). The results of the analyses are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Summary of confirmatory factor analysis

Items	Significant test of parameter estimation				Item Reliability		Composite Reliability	Convergence Validity	
	Unstd	S.E.	C.R.	p	Factor Loading	SMC	CR	AVE	
Brand Awareness	ba1	1.000			0.860	0.740	0.914	0.681	
	ba2	0.944	0.046	20.330	0.000	0.771			0.594
	ba3	1.060	0.040	26.362	0.000	0.897			0.805
	ba4	0.940	0.046	20.402	0.000	0.803			0.596
	ba5	0.927	0.049	18.893	0.000	0.788			0.541
Brand Image	bi1	1.000			0.910	0.829	0.963	0.814	
	bi2	0.991	0.028	34.893	0.000	0.927			0.860
	bi3	1.075	0.027	37.660	0.000	0.950			0.902
	bi4	1.007	0.030	34.085	0.000	0.920			0.847
	bi5	0.922	0.036	25.386	0.000	0.818			0.669
	bi6	0.926	0.031	30.320	0.000	0.882			0.778
Brand Trust	bt1	1.000			0.877	0.769	0.907	0.710	
	bt2	1.045	0.038	27.499	0.000	0.897			0.805
	bt3	0.843	0.038	22.331	0.000	0.803			0.644
	bt4	0.854	0.039	21.629	0.000	0.788			0.621
Perceived Fit	fit1	1.000			0.886	0.785	0.955	0.842	
	fit2	1.020	0.032	31.875	0.000	0.928			0.860
	fit3	0.993	0.032	30.728	0.000	0.914			0.836
	fit4	1.026	0.031	33.042	0.000	0.941			0.885
Attitude	att1	1.000			0.918	0.843	0.947	0.697	
	att2	1.051	0.027	38.814	0.000	0.949			0.900
	att3	1.003	0.029	34.052	0.000	0.912			0.831
	att4	1.029	0.028	37.069	0.000	0.936			0.877
	att5	0.542	0.049	8.928	0.000	0.591			0.153
	att6	0.986	0.030	33.252	0.000	0.905			0.818
	att7	0.532	0.041	10.628	0.000	0.554			0.206
	att8	0.898	0.036	25.177	0.000	0.808			0.653
Purchase Intention	pi1	1.000			0.949	0.900	0.957	0.847	
	pi2	1.020	0.021	49.183	0.000	0.976			0.952
	pi3	0.880	0.032	27.208	0.000	0.816			0.667
	pi4	0.878	0.031	28.654	0.000	0.933			0.695

4.3. Discriminant validity

To determine the discriminant validity of the scale, the Fornell-Larcker criterion coefficients proposed by Fornell and Larcker (1981) were calculated. According to the Fornell and Larcker (1981) criterion, the square root of the AVE values of the scales used in the research should be higher than the correlations between the variables. All of the scales used in the study meet the specified criteria. The Fornell-Larcker criterion coefficients are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Discriminant validity analysis

	BA	BI	BT	FIT	ATT	PI
BA	0.825					
BI	0.705	0.902				
BT	0.751	0.742	0.843			
FIT	0.777	0.695	0.732	0.918		
ATT	0.307	0.245	0.301	0.324	0.835	
PI	0.745	0.688	0.757	0.782	0.356	0.920

4.4. Model fit assessment

The research model was tested using CFA. One modification was made to obtain acceptable fit values. The fit values obtained from the CFA are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Model fit index

Fit index	Allowable range	Research model fit
χ^2	The smaller the better	1618.248
df	The larger the better	416
χ^2/df	≤ 5	3.890
NFI	≥ 0.90	0.909
RFI	≥ 0.90	0.900
IFI	≥ 0.90	0.931
TLI	≥ 0.90	0.923
CFI	≥ 0.90	0.931
SRMR	≤ 0.08	0.049
RMSEA	≤ 0.08	0.078

4.5. Hypothesis tests

When testing hypotheses, R^2 values were examined first. The R^2 value indicates how much of the variance in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables. The results of the SEM analysis are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. SEM structure model

In this study, the explained variance score (R^2) for the effect of parent brand awareness, parent brand image, and parent brand trust on perceived fit is 0,75. The explained variance score (R^2) for the effect of perceived brand fit and attitude toward the extension brand on the extension brand purchase intention is 0,66. This research model demonstrates good explanatory power. The regression analysis results are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. List of regression a nalysis

Dependent variable	Independent variable	Unstandardized regression coefficient	S.E.	C.R.	p	Standardized regression coefficient	R ²
FIT	BA	0.682	0.081	8.427	0.000	0.587	0.754
	BI	0.199	0.061	3.259	0.001	0.153	
	BT	0.200	0.079	2.529	0.011	0.177	
ATT	FIT	0.402	0.050	8.105	0.000	0.372	0.138
	ATT	0.067	0.029	2.303	0.021	0.073	0.663

Table 5 shows that parent brand awareness (Unstand.=0,682; C.R.=8,427; p=0,000), parent brand image (Unstand.=0,199; C.R.=3,259; p=0,001), and parent brand trust (Unstand.=0,200; C.R.=2,529; p=0,011) have a positive effect on perceived fit. These findings support hypotheses H₁, H₂, and H₃. Perceived fit also has a positive effect on attitudes toward brand extension (Unstand.=0,402; C.R.=8,105; p=0,000). This finding supports hypothesis H₄. In addition, perceived fit (Unstand.=0,768; C.R.=20,366; p=0,000) and attitude toward the extension brand (Unstand.=0,067; C.R.=2,303; p=0,021) have a positive effect on the extension brand purchase intention. These findings support hypotheses H₅ and H₆.

4.6. Analysis on mediating effect

After hypothesis testing, mediation effect were examined. The mediation analysis included total, direct, and indirect effect. The results of the analysis are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Analysis of mediating model indirect effect

Effect	Point estimate	Product coefficients		Bootstrap 5000 times	
		S.E.	p	Bias corrected 95%	
				Lower bound	Upper bound
Standardized total effect FIT→PI	0.811	0.024	0.000	0.760	0.856
Standardized direct effect FIT→PI	0.784	0.028	0.000	0.727	0.834
Standardized indirect effect FIT→ATT→PI	0.027	0.011	0.007	0.007	0.052

Table 6 shows that perceived fit has an indirect effect on extension brand purchase intention through attitude towards the extension brand (Point Est.=0,027; p=0,007; [0,007 - 0,052]). This finding supports hypothesis H₇.

5. Discussions

This study, which examines the effects of perceived fit on parent brand awareness, parent brand image, and parent brand trust, and the effect of perceived fit on attitudes towards the brand extension and purchase intention, shows that the success of brand extension is significantly influenced by the similarity and fit of product categories, as well as consumers' perceptions of the parent brand.

The findings indicate that parent brand awareness has a positive effect on perceived fit. This finding supports the consumer-based brand equity approach, which suggests that consumers rate products from brands they are familiar with as more acceptable (Keller, 1993). Similarly, the positive effect of parent brand image and parent brand trust on perceived fit shows that consumers use not only product features but also associations and perceptions of trust related to the parent brand when evaluating extension products. These findings are consistent with studies showing that brand image and brand trust play a significant role in perceived fit (Peng et al., 2023; Li et al., 2026).

Another finding of the study is that perceived fit positively influences attitudes toward brand extension and brand extension purchase intention. This finding supports the fit effect, which is consistently emphasized in the brand extension literature (Aaker & Keller, 1990). Studies also

highlight that when consumers establish a meaningful relationship between the parent brand and the extension brand, their attitudes towards the extension brand are more positive, and purchase intentions are more easily formed (Mathur et al., 2023; Peng et al., 2023). Therefore, consumers perceiving the extension brand as fit with the parent brand identity can be considered a fundamental element for the success of the extension strategy.

Another finding is that attitude towards the extension brand positively influences the brand extension purchase intention. This finding suggests that consumers' overall assessments of the extension brand are a significant determinant in the formation of their behavioral intentions. In other words, consumers are not only evaluating the parent brand versus the extension brand, but they are also transforming this evaluation into attitudes that shape their purchase intentions.

One of the most important findings of the study is that perceived fit has an indirect effect on brand extension purchase intention through attitudes toward the brand extension. This finding suggests that consumers' perceived fit not only directly translates into purchase intention but also first fosters a positive attitude towards the brand extension, and that purchase intention emerges as a result of these attitudinal assessments. This finding is consistent with the literature that highlights the important role of attitude in brand development efforts (Czellar, 2003). Furthermore, the findings suggest that brand extension success should be explained not only by cognitive fit assessments but also by attitudinal processes.

6. Conclusions

When the research findings are evaluated, the study reveals that perceptions of brand equity should be considered together with consumer-based psychological mechanisms in explaining the success of brand extension strategies. Especially in today's world, where brands are increasingly entering new product categories, studies show that image, trust perceptions, and awareness levels towards the parent brand are of strategic importance in the acceptance of an extension product by the consumer. Therefore, businesses need to focus not only on developing extension products but also on building strong brand perceptions and transferring these perceptions to extension products.

6.1. Theoretical implications

This research makes significant theoretical contributions to the brand extension literature. First, the study supports the importance of consumer-based brand equity components in the success of a brand extension strategy by revealing the impact of parent brand awareness, parent brand image, and parent brand trust on perceived fit. Furthermore, the research shows that perceived fit effects brand extension purchase intention not only directly but also indirectly through attitudes toward the brand extension. This finding demonstrates that in brand extension evaluations, cognitive evaluations are transformed into behavioral outcomes through attitudinal processes, leading to a better understanding of consumer decision-making mechanisms. This study expands the scope of the brand extension literature by integrating consumer-based brand equity approaches with consumer attitude theories within a comprehensive framework.

6.2. Limitations

This study has some limitations. Firstly, the research was conducted using data obtained only from 472 participants living in Tokat. Therefore, the generalizability of the findings is limited. Secondly, using convenience sampling as a sampling method limits the sample's ability to represent the population and increases the risk of sampling bias. The fact that the data was collected using a survey technique based on participants' self-reports may lead to a risk of social desirability bias. Finally, the study has a cross-sectional design. Therefore, it is not possible to reach definitive conclusions about causality.

6.3. Recommendations

When developing brand extension strategies, businesses should focus not only on product features and similarities between product categories, but also on strengthening consumers' trust in, image, and awareness of the parent brand. It is also recommended that the relationship between the parent brand and the extension brand be communicated to consumers through effective communication efforts during new product launches.

Future studies are recommended to include variables such as perceived risk, brand identification, brand love, and brand loyalty, which can influence the success of brand extension strategies, in the model. Furthermore, studies conducted in different cultural contexts, sectors, and product categories will increase the generalizability of the results. In addition, experimental designs and longitudinal studies can be used to track how consumer attitudes toward brand extension change over time.

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